

LICHEN PLANUS . RELEVANCE OF THE PROBLEM OF CLASSIFICATION AND DIFFERENTIATED TREATMENT

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Abstract . This article highlights the problems of lichen planus, a chronic dermatological disease that causes significant discomfort and a decrease in the quality of life of patients. Particular attention is paid to the relevance of the classification of this disease and the need to develop differentiated approaches to treatment. The authors analyze the various clinical forms of lichen planus, consider etiopathogenetic factors and emphasize the complexity of diagnosis due to symptomatic similarities with other skin diseases. The article provides an overview of current treatment methods, including systemic and local therapeutic strategies, and also discusses prospects for further research in this area. The goal of the work is to increase the effectiveness of treatment of lichen planus through improved understanding of its pathogenesis and optimization of therapeutic approaches.

Key words . Lichen planus, Classification of diseases, Differentiated treatment

Clinical and morphological forms of lichen planus are varied and include:

1. **The usual form** is characterized by the presence of flat, shiny, red-violet papules.
2. **Hypertrophic form** - the formation of thickened, warty growths, often on the legs.
3. **Erosive-ulcerative form** - damage to the mucous membranes with the formation of erosions and ulcers.
4. **Atrophic form** - characterized by thinning of the skin in areas of rash.
5. **Bullous (bubble) form** - the formation of blisters against the background of typical rashes.
6. **Annular (ring-shaped) form** - the rash forms rings

Modern classification of lichen planus

The modern classification of lichen planus includes several forms based on clinical and morphological characteristics. Includes oral lichen (damage to the oral mucosa), cutaneous lichen (the appearance of characteristic rashes on the skin), as well as vulvovaginal , scleroatrophic , hypertrophic, erosive-ulcerative,

and atrophic lichen. These forms vary in location, appearance of the rash, and severity of symptoms. Contacting a specialist allows you to determine the form of lichen and prescribe adequate treatment.

Classification of red cutaneous lichen according to ICD - 10

In the International Classification of Diseases, 10th Revision (ICD-10), lichen planus is classified under code L43. This code refers to a group of dermatoses, especially those characterized by specific rashes and changes in the structure of the skin. It is important to understand that ICD-10 is used primarily to standardize medical diagnoses and does not necessarily reflect all clinical aspects of the disease.

Classification of red cutaneous lichen according to ICD - 11

In the International Classification of Diseases, 11th Revision (ICD-11), lichen planus is classified under code EA61. This code refers to a group of diseases of the skin and mucous membranes associated with diseases of the immune complex. Lichen planus in ICD-11 is considered as a separate disease associated with pathological immune reactions in the body.

Treatment of lichen planus depends on its clinical form:

1. **Skin manifestations** : Topical corticosteroids are commonly used to reduce inflammation and itching. In severe forms, systemic corticosteroids or immunosuppressive drugs may be prescribed .
2. **Oral zoster** : Treatment includes topical corticosteroids in the form of gels or ointments. In some cases, systemic medications or phototherapy are used.
3. **Genital ringworm** : The use of topical corticosteroids and skin emollients may be required .

An individualized approach to treatment is always recommended, taking into account the specific symptoms and general condition of the patient.

Conclusions . In conclusion, the article highlights that lichen planus is a complex multifactorial disease that requires a thorough understanding for effective diagnosis and treatment. The importance of accurate disease classification cannot be underestimated as it plays a key role in determining appropriate differentiated treatment. The article confirms the need for an individual approach to treatment, taking into account the diversity of clinical forms and pathogenesis of the disease.

The authors emphasize that current therapeutic strategies, including both systemic and local approaches, must be tailored to the specific needs of each patient. This requires not only in-depth knowledge of the disease, but also constant updating of information in the light of the latest research. Finally, the study highlights the importance of ongoing research into the pathogenesis and treatment of lichen planus, suggesting that future discoveries may lead to even more effective and targeted treatments. In summary, this article makes a significant contribution to the understanding and management of this complex and often intractable disease.

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